

Analysis of industrial waste heat potential used for novel thermally driven sorption chiller concepts - the RE-WITCH project

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Abstract

The industrial sector in the EU, accounting for 25.1% of final energy consumption in 2022, requires significant efforts to achieve decarbonization, as only 10.1% of its fuel consumption comes from renewables. Thermal processes, consuming two-thirds of industrial energy, present opportunities for renewable energy integration and waste heat utilization. The RE-WITCH project addresses these challenges by developing and implementing innovative thermally driven cooling solutions across four industrial sites in Poland, Spain, Greece, and Italy. Each demo case demonstrates unique waste heat characteristics and cooling demands, utilizing adsorption and absorption chillers. For example, waste heat from brewery processes, food processing systems, CHP units in biofuel production, and air compressors in paper manufacturing is harnessed. Preliminary energy analysis highlights varying waste heat capacities (85–550 kW) and operational schedules. The project promotes energy efficiency, primary energy savings, and GHG reduction, contributing to the broader adoption of renewable cooling solutions in industry.

Keywords: Waste heat, Industry, Cooling, Energy Efficiency

Introduction/Background

The industrial sector is responsible for 25.1% of final energy consumption the EU in 2022 ([nrg_bal_c](#)). Renewables and biofuels make only 10.1% in the fuel consumption in the industry (ibid). This shows that great effort is needed to achieve a full decarbonisation of the European industry. The European Union supports enterprises on the path towards more efficient energy consumption and renewable energy transition. The Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net Zero Industrial Act among others are tools to do so.

Thermal processes are the essential consumers within the industry, making up about 2/3 in the final energy consumption (Meyer et al., 2024). Many processes operate in low and medium temperature levels, being feasible for the direct integration of waste heat or renewable energies, such as solar thermal. The re-integration of waste heat and new integration of renewable heat are key solutions to lower the fossil fuel consumption in the industry. Especially the coupling of low

temperature waste heat and sorption chillers has a great potential industrial applications (Frazzica et al. 2021).

The RE-WITCH project is directly this issue of renewable and energy efficient cooling solutions in the industry. As a part of the project, innovative thermally driven cooling solutions using absorption and adsorption chillers are being developed and installed in four different industrial sites in Spain, Greece, Poland, and Italy.

Discussion and Results

The analysis of available waste heat in the industrial sites is an essential part to both assess and compare the waste heat and to identify opportunities for cooling system integration. The quality of waste heat and the local cooling demand are individual characteristics, making it challenging to develop standardised waste heat-to-cold solutions.

Demo 1: Brewery in Poland

The brewing process is highly feasible for the integration of renewable heat and cold, as the maximum required temperature is at about 100 °C. Furthermore, the heating and cooling of beer and wort tanks can be coupled, using the available waste heat directly to drive sorption chiller. The RE-WITCH project will implement an adsorption chiller to cool down a 30 m³ storage wort. Initially, the wort has a temperature of about 98 °C after the boiling process. Afterwards, the wort must be cooled down to a temperature level of below 10 °C in a time frame of two hours. Heat is extracted from the wort as it is channelled through a heat exchanger to harness heat at 90 °C to run the adsorption chiller. The adsorption chiller generates cold at about 7 °C. An additional electric driven vapor compression chiller provides cooling at lower temperature to cool down the wort to the desired temperature. It also serves as a back-up system.

Demo 2: Food processing in Spain

The food industry is characterized by a great variety of thermal processes in both heating and cooling applications, dependent on the final food product and the manufactured food products. This demo is different from the other three RE-WITCH demos, as waste heat is not used to drive the chiller, but the heated cooling water from the chiller is used to provide heat to the local process heat system. Cold well water is heated to a level of 60 °C to 65 °C and fed into existing hot water storages.

Demo 3: Biofuel production in Greece

The demo in Greece is part of the biofuel production industry. Biogas is produced using feedstock wastewater and glycerol from biodiesel production units, as well as other biogenic products originating from other facilities in the region around the factory, such as olive oil, and edible oil mills. The site operating all day and all year. The biogas is used to run three CHP units for electricity generation. Some heat is required for the biodiesel production on site. But the vast majority of the heat generated in the by the CHP units is not required for further processing, and thus labelled in the following as waste heat. Additionally, the plant requires cooling for both the biodiesel units and the biogas production process in the digester. This makes availability of waste heat and simultaneous demand for cooling makes the integration of sorption highly interesting. The waste heat is harnessed through water heat exchanger in parallel directly at the biogas CHP units. The temperature of the waste heat water stream is then lifted from exhaust gas in additional heat

exchangers. The waste heat water stream is then at $> 95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and supplied to the absorption chiller. The innovative absorption chiller is planned to provide cold at two separate temperature levels, which requires a duplication of evaporator/ absorber pair. This allows cold supply at both $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the digester. Another aspect of this demo is the operation of an ORC unit to generate additionally electricity for selling market.

Demo 4: Paper manufacturing in Italy

The paper manufacturing site in Italy is the fourth demo of the RE-WITCH project. The temperature ranges required in the paper industry is feasible for the integration of renewable energies and waste heat recovery. The RE-WITCH system in Italy will harness waste heat from compressors. Air-to-water heat exchanger equipped to the compressor will generate hot water at a temperature of $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This waste heat is then used to drive an adsorption chiller. More information will be collected in the up-coming months on the operation cycle. The chiller will provide cooling capacity at 80 kW.

Energy Analysis

A first energy analysis on the waste heat in the different demo sites shows what energy is available to drive the sorption chillers. The sites differ a lot in the temperature and mass flow of waste heat. The operational schedule will be screened in detail to create a greater picture. The table below shows the fundamental characteristics of the waste heat in the 4 demo sites.

	Waste heat source	Temperature	Mass flow	Th. Capacity
Demo 1	Beer wort	$90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$28\text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$	326 kW
Demo 2	Sorption chiller	$60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$1.6\text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$	85 kW
Demo 3	CHP units	$99\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	-	550 kW
Demo 4	Air compressors	$75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$13\text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$	150 kW

With more information available in 2025, primary energy savings and savings in GHG emissions will be calculated and integrated.

Summary/Conclusions

The decarbonisation of industrial manufacturing and process lines is a great challenge in the EU. Increased energy efficiency within not only specific components, but also the total industrial site is crucial for making progress. The utilisation of industrial waste heat as either a heat source for industrial heat pumps or to directly supply thermally driven chillers with energy is a great solution with potential in nearly all industrial fields.

The RE-WITCH project contributes to the acceptance and roll-out of thermally driven chillers, both adsorption and absorption, to provide renewable cold for industrial processes. Four individual demo cases with their individual requirements and features are covered by the project. The initial step is to identify the local characteristics, demands and opportunities of waste heat harnessing and utilisation.

The integration of the renewable cold will increase the total energy efficiency, the reduction of primary energy consumption and subsequently generate GHG savings. The nominal COP of the thermally driven chillers lies between 0.5 and 0.8. The different applications differ in the thermal capacity from < 100 kW to 550 kW. Also, the operational schedules show great deviations, from a constant time per day, to multiple hours of incantations operation to nearly 24/7 operation.

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